

ON RHYME PHRASEOLOGISMS IN FRENCH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.

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It is not enough to classify phraseologisms in French and Uzbek according to a certain word group and to study their grammatical features. In the process of grammatical analysis of rhyming expressions, we can witness that among the total 250 examples collected in French, noun, verb, pronoun, adjective, adverb word groups have formed mutual rhyming. In addition, not only one type of word groups do not rhyme with each other, but two different word groups also play an important role in the formation of mutually rhyming phrases. In addition to such rhyming, we can witness the formation of rhyming phraseological units as a result of the combination of prepositions.

Key words: adverbial phrase, character, expression, word group, types of pronoun, phraseological units;

Rhyming in adverb vocabulary.

The adverbial phrase also indicates the sign of the object as well as the quality. But if the adjective is used before the noun, the adverb is used before the verb and defines its character. And the work shows the time, speed, amount, position, place, reason, purpose of the action. We will analyze rhyming phrases in the Ravish vocabulary in two.

- 1- Rhyming phrases consisting of whole parts;
 - 2- Phraseological units consisting of rhyming words.
- Examples of rhyming phrases made up of whole parts:

de gré à gré → by mutual agreement;

Bon gré- mal gré → against the will;

Accord de gré à gré → bilateral agreement;

Au fur et à mesure → as far as possible, constantly.

Since such expressions are completely rhetorical, it is not possible to analyze them separately. Among the rhyming phraseological expressions in the Uzbek language, we did not find such catchy expressions.

An example of phraseological units with rhyming words only:

Qui trop se hâte en cheminant

En bon chemin se fourvoie souvent; (a girl in a hurry doesn't get on the ground)

In this proverb, en cheminant expresses the meaning of the state of advanced, hasty approach. In the sentence, this adverb has the function of circumstantial (circonstanciel de manière), and the adverb souvent-tez is used as the adverb of tense in the sentence (circonstanciel de temps). In phraseological units, units expressed by rhyming words are few in French. In the Uzbek language, we did not find such stable compounds.

Rhyming in pronouns.

If we talk about the word group of pronouns, it is a group of words without meaning that replaces a word, a phrase, a part of a sentence, or even a whole sentence. There are seven types of pronouns, and only four of the rhyming phrases are based on the combination of pronouns. Two of the pronouns are independent personal pronouns (pronom personnelle tonique) and the rest are suspect, interrogative, individuation, and personal pronouns. For example:

Aujourd'hui à moi,
Demain à toi.

(Don't laugh at someone, Zinhor, there are people who laugh at you too).

Or: Quel pour moi
Tel pour toi. (greeting).

Both of these examples count the independent personal pronouns moi and toi (les pronoms indépendant). But since the concept of independent personal pronouns or independent personal pronouns does not exist in the Uzbek language, a similar proverb to this French rhyming phraseological unit was not found in the Uzbek language. In the second example, there is another pair of rhyming pronouns, which are the interrogative pronoun and the demonstrative pronoun tel- so.

Phonetics is related to other areas of language, because there is no syllable, word, phrase without sound, stress and tone. Because of this, phonetics is considered a language stage related to lexis, morphology, syntax and stylistics. In linguistics, within the framework of phonetics, speech sounds are mainly studied in their articulatory, acoustic, perceptive and functional aspects, tone, syllable, syntagma, stress, etc.

The role of nasal sounds in French is very important in the formation of rhyme in rhyming phraseological units. On the other hand, we can see that the role of these sounds in the Uzbek language is less than in the French language.

Analyzing the rhyming phraseological units, we can see that in the French rhyming phraseological units we can find a lot of open syllabic harmony. In the Uzbek language, as we said above, we find fewer phraseological units with such an open rhyme than in the French language, which is also due to the unique characteristics of both languages.

In the course of the morphological analysis of rhyming phraseological units, we have seen that in the French language, the noun group is more common than other word groups. But if we analyze the types of horses, the least common of them was the participation of horses. In both French and French, you can find rhyming phraseological units involving countable and uncountable nouns. The above examples are evidence that confirms our statement.

In the process of morphological analysis, we saw that the verb is in the passive part of the word group in both languages. In the analysis of the verb word group within both languages, the specificity between the languages was more visible than that of the noun word group.

Language also has form and meaning. In language, form means sound, the material of language. This is also called the expression plan of the language. The sound is represented by a letter in the text. On this basis, the form of pronunciation and the form of writing are different. We often record the phenomenon of language.

The phonetic and morphological aspects of the rhyming phraseological unit components, which are the research object of this work, were considered above through their examples.

The phrase corresponds to a certain group of words in terms of meaning and grammar, therefore it is an answer to a certain question as a whole and acts as a certain part of a sentence in a sentence. For example, he was fed up with all his work (filler) until he blinked his eyes for two days (hol). It can be seen that the rhyming words in the rhyming phraseological units are also among nouns, pronouns, adverbs, verbs, adjectives, adverbs and mixed words. This is also reflected in the above analysis of French and Uzbek rhyming phraseological units.

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